

E4.2 Intermediate prototype for zero-touch and proactive network management

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List of Acronyms

3D	Three Dimension
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOps	AI Operations
AR	Augmented Reality
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
6DoF	Six Degrees of Freedom
FPS	Frame per Second
HD	High Definition
HTC	Holographic-Type Communications
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NR	New Radio
QoE	Quality of Experience
RAN	Radio Access Network
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TD	Technological Domain
UE	User Equipment
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

1 Introduction

Based on the architecture described in Deliverable E4.3.2 "Initial Design of Zero-Touch and Proactive Network Management", we will explore the implementation phase of the described architecture. This implementation aims to create proactive and autonomous network management for future 6G infrastructures. Using the advanced Neuro-Symbolic (NeSy) AI framework, especially Logic Tensor Networks (LTN), this implementation offers an efficient CPU resource prediction service. The main goal is to balance the trade-off between providing too many and too few resources, ensuring the network runs smoothly and efficiently.

This is an *accompanying document to the full prototype already uploaded on the corresponding GitLab repository and not in itself a deliverable*. This document serves as a practical complement to the theoretical insights provided in the original deliverable, bridging the gap between conceptual understanding and actionable implementation. By the end of this guide, readers will be equipped with the knowledge to replicate and extend this implementation for further research and development in zero-touch network management.

2 Technical requirements description

The Logic Tensor Networks (LTN) Python module offers a powerful framework for integrating symbolic reasoning and neural network learning, providing a robust approach to Neuro-Symbolic AI. By combining logical constraints with the flexibility and learning capabilities of neural networks, the LTN module enables the creation of models that are not only data-driven but also adhere to specified logical relationships. This integration facilitates the development of more interpretable and logically consistent models, which is particularly beneficial in complex domains where understanding the reasoning behind model predictions is crucial.

In the context of 6GENABLERS, utilizing the LTN module becomes particularly advantageous. The future 6G networks will be characterized by unprecedented connectivity demands and highly dynamic environments requiring real-time responsiveness and seamless performance. Ensuring optimal network performance involves making precise and proactive resource management decisions, such as CPU resource allocation. LTN allows for embedding domain-specific knowledge and logical constraints directly into the machine learning models used for these predictions, thereby enhancing their accuracy and reliability. The use of LTN aligns with the goals of the 6GENABLERS project by providing a sophisticated tool to balance the trade-offs between resource over-provisioning and under-provisioning, ensuring that network resources are used efficiently and effectively. This results in better anticipation of network needs and more informed decision-making, critical for achieving zero-touch and proactive network management in 6G networks.

The installation of the LTN module is done as follows:

```
python3 pip install ltn
```

And then we can use it in a Python code in this way:

```
import tensorflow as tf import ltn
```

Some of the basic functionalities of the LTN modules are the definition of *predicates and axioms*:

```
# Predicates (Equality)
alpha = 0.99
eq = ltn.Predicate.Lambda(lambda args: exp(),axis=1))
# fuzzy logic
forall =
ltn Wrapper_Quantifier(ltn.fuzzy_ops.Aggreg_pMeanError(p=2),se
mantics="forall")
```

And finally, the creation of the neural networks would be something like this:

```
f = ltn.Function.MLP([X], [Y], hidden_layer_sizes=(Z,T))
```

3 Configuration

There are four main phases in the code: Obtaining the data, initial setup and optimization loop and model confidence check.

- During the first phase the dataset is obtained, cleaned and prepared to its use. The values are formatted in the proper way and the metrics are defined.
- In the second phase, the NeSy model is described through Python, including the predicates and axioms using LTN. Additionally, the architecture of the Machine Learning model is defined.

```
dx, dy = np.c_[df.iloc[:, :]], df.iloc[:, :]
scaler_model = MinMaxScaler()
scaler_model.fit(dx)
X_full = np.array(pd.DataFrame(scaler_model.transform(dx)))
y_full = np.array(np.expand_dims(dy, axis=1))
n_features = X_full[0].shape[0]
n_classes = y_full[0].shape[0]
x_train, y_train, x_test, y_test = X_full[0:., :], y_full[0:D, :],
X_full[D:L, :], y_full[D:L, :]
```

- The third phase is one of the most important as it is in charge of the optimization and training loop of the model. It ensures that the model parameters improve iteratively to enhance an accurate prediction while keeping to logical constraints. By balancing the success of logical axioms and minimizing SLA violations, the model effectively manages CPU resources in a zero-touch, proactive manner, aligning with the goals of the 6GENABLERS project. The process begins with the initial setup, where a learning rate and a decay are defined. We also initialize the Adadelta optimizer with the previous learning rate parameters. The Adadelta optimizer is an optimization algorithm designed for training machine learning models, particularly neural networks. The main goal of the optimizer is to address some of the neural networks' limitations, especially the issue of decreasing learning rates over time. Adadelta adapts the learning rates based on a moving window of gradient updates, helping to maintain a more consistent learning rate throughout the training process. Next, we set a threshold value for CPU usage. This threshold helps evaluate the Service Level Agreement (SLA) compliance. The training process runs for a predefined iterations. During each iteration the axioms' function is called with the training data calculating the satisfaction level (sat) of the logical axioms, which measures how well the model's predictions adhere to the logical constraints. The loss function is then called to calculate the SLA loss based on the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the predicted values against the lower bound defined by the CPU threshold. The total loss is computed as $1 - \text{sat} + \text{sla}$, combining the satisfaction level (which we aim to maximize) and the SLA loss (which we aim to minimize). Using the recorded records in each iteration, we compute the gradients of the loss with respect to the model's trainable variables. These gradients are clipped to a range of $[-1.0, 1.0]$ to prevent excessive updates that could destabilize the training

process. The optimizer then updates the model's parameters using the clipped gradients.

During this training process, the model parameters are iteratively adjusted to improve prediction accuracy while maintaining logical consistency with the defined constraints. By incorporating logical axioms into the loss function, the model learns to make predictions that are not only accurate but also logically consistent.

```
cpu_th = np.mean(y_test)
for epoch in range(epochs):
    with tf.GradientTape() as tape:
        sat = axioms(x_train, y_train)
        cpu_lower_bound = cpu_th
        sla = sla_loss(x_train, cpu_lower_bound)
        loss = 1. - sat + sla
```

- Finally, we evaluate the confidence metric that quantify the model trustworthiness and reliability. By creating a modified dataset through a probabilistic masking approach and passing this data through the trained model, the function generates new predictions. These predictions are then evaluated to see how many of the previously non-compliant samples did not change their group to become compliant. The confidence metric is calculated as the ratio of these SLA-compliant predictions to the total number of initially violating samples. This metric provides insight into the model's ability to maintain the prediction within the original group (or class in classification tasks), i.e., a sample is compliant/incompliant with SLA in both original and masked dataset predictions. A high confidence metric indicates that a significant proportion of previously compliant samples are still predicted to fall within the acceptable CPU utilization range. A low confidence metric would imply that many samples still violate the SLA even after adjustments, indicating a need for further model refinement or a different approach to data masking. A usage snippet of `masked_data_pred()` is as follows:

```
y_mask = masked_data_pred(shap_v, x_test, true_index)
indexes_tensor = tf.convert_to_tensor(true_index)
sla_mask = tf.gather(y_mask, indexes_tensor)
conform = sla_mask < cpu_th
con_count = np.sum(conform)
confidence_metric = np.nan_to_num(con_count / sam_count, nan=0)
```

4 Results

- We can generate the graph that represents the satisfaction levels of the logical axioms over the epochs during the training process. In the training process we have stored the satisfaction levels of the logical axioms that have been evaluated at regular intervals. At each of these epochs, the logical axioms are evaluated using the current state of the model. The satisfaction level is computed and then plotted, as can be shown in Figure 1. This metric represents how well the model's predictions are. As we can see, the plot presents an increasing trend, showing that the model is progressively satisfying the logical axioms better as the training process progresses.

Figure 1 Satisfaction levels through the epochs

Additionally, the CDF of predictions showed in Figure 2 represents the cumulative probability distribution of the model's predictions for CPU utilization, indicating the proportion of predictions that are below that value.

Figure 2 Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of CPU predictions for lower bound 0.3

The CDF of predictions plot provides a visual of the cumulative probability distribution of the predicted CPU utilization values from the trained model. This plot is used for understanding the distribution and variability of the model’s predictions and evaluating how well the model adheres to specified SLA requirements. The CDF curve depicted in Figure 2 shows that only are violating the CPU lower bound of 0.3. This is further clarified by the time series comparison of measured and predicted CPU, where both curves

Figure 3 Measured vs. Predicted CPU utilization

The obtained confidence score is

confidence metric 0.966

5 Conclusion

In this document, we have explored the practical implementation of the innovative Neuro-Symbolic (NeSy) AI framework, specifically focusing on Logic Tensor Networks (LTN), to address the critical needs of proactive and zero-touch network management in 6G networks. By using LTN, we have demonstrated a sophisticated approach to CPU resource prediction, balancing the trade-offs between resource over-provisioning and under-provisioning, which is essential for maintaining optimal network performance and efficiency.

The integration of logical constraints into neural network training through LTN offers a unique advantage for 6G enablers, providing models that are not only accurate but also interpretable and logically consistent. This alignment with logical rules ensures that resource management decisions are both data-driven and grounded in domain-specific knowledge, enhancing the reliability and robustness of the network management processes.

In conclusion, the adoption of the LTN framework within the 6GENABLERS project represents a significant step forward in the journey towards future-proof 6G networks. It highlights the importance of integrating advanced AI techniques with logical reasoning to meet the sophisticated demands of next-generation network management, ultimately paving the way for more intelligent, reliable, and efficient 6G infrastructures.